

ASSESSMENT OF THE SANITARY CONDITION OF THE WATER OF THE AKHANGARAN RIVER USING THE SAPROBIC ALGAE INDEX

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Abstract: the article is devoted to the study of the influence of anthropogenic and man-made factors on the water quality of the Akhangaran River. The study of the species composition of algae and their distribution along the Akhangaran River is very relevant today, since the formation and functioning of hydrobiocenoses of the river depend on algal communities. Water quality control in the river is currently one of the pressing problems.

Key words: Akhangaran River, aquatic environment, indicator saprobic types of algae, water quality of the Akhangaran River, bioindication, hydrobiocenoses, equitability.

Introduction: One important area for monitoring the natural aquatic environment is the use of indicators. Thus, according to scientific sources [1, 2, 3] indicator saprobic species of algae are capable of growing in both the cleanest and most polluted reservoirs. Based on the composition of the flora of algae in reservoirs and their quantitative indicator, the degree of water pollution can be determined. The relevance of this work increases with the fact that today there is information about the atlas of algae, which are indicators of the saprobity of water in the river. Akhangaran, absent.

Analysis of literature on the topic: Algal biological diversity is determined through morphological trait analysis combined with ecology and geographic distribution (Vinogradova, 1978). Since the algae of continental waters are mostly single-celled forms, united by mechanisms of coloniality, cenobility, etc. aggregation, the importance of cell morphology becomes decisive for systematics. Morphological characteristics of identifiable algal cells lead to the determination of not only species affiliation, but also make it possible in some cases to isolate intraspecific taxa – varieties and forms.

The collection of algal species in a given area makes up its algoflora. Analysis of algoflora, as a system of cohabiting and evolving populations of species according to B.A. Yurtsev (1968, 1982), is carried out on the basis of species diversity reflected in the list composition of flora.

The diversity structure includes taxonomic-level alpha diversity, phytocenotic-level beta diversity (variety of plant communities), and biogeographic-level gamma diversity (diversity of phytochories) (Whittaker, 1975, 1977). The overall diversity of plant life is in principle determined by the contributions of all three levels, but both the historical and functional aspects of the interactions between them are still very poorly understood (Krassilov, 2003). The idea of diversity brings together many concepts and terms, including – “species richness” and “equitability” or uniformity (Peet, 1974). In the work of N.V. Kondratieva (2000) elaborated on the views that became available to the international community in 2001. (Kondratyeva, 2001), on various aspects of the classification and analysis of diversity in algae, which absorb all the problems that exist in this area of science at present [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

Materials and methods. Assessment of the state of the first trophic link is possible using indicators of abundance and biomass, biochemical oxygen consumption (BOD), water oxygen saturation, water transparency and primary production related to transparency, as well as the saprobity index. These indicators change naturally in the surface water ecosystem and can be classified according to system B. Sladcheka [10].

Various characteristics of aquatic ecosystems are assessed using this method. Its widest applicability is for assessing water quality (Chukhlebova, Dogadina, 1975; Abakumov, 1978; Gavrishova, 1981; Osamu, 1975; Van Landingham, 1976), but heavy metals are also identified by teratology (Saboski, 1977), mutagenicity (Sharma, 1989), toxicity (Braginsky, 1981), typological levels of systems (Leynaud, 1975), habitat and specific contamination (Whitton, 1975). An indication is used for the type of use (Gurariy, Shine, 1974), the intensity of self-purification from pesticides (Kranoperova, 1994; Mingazova, Zakirov, Derevenskaya, etc., 1994; Abd El-Magid, 1986) and copper (Sathya, 1988), paleoindication of temperature conditions and water chemistry is carried out (Zubovich, 1989). The sanitary and biological state of the reservoir is determined by indicators (Vánčsa, 1984) and even the assessment of aquatic ecosystems (Konstantinov, 1978; Gavrishova, 1981), which, when analyzed, turns out to be an assessment of water quality. Indication is recommended as a basis for quality control of the environment and decision-making system (Siepel, 1996). In all the analyzed works, bioindication methods are not used systematically, although in connection with individual environmental factors, therefore we consider private approaches to have no prospects for assessing the state of aquatic ecosystems [1, 2, 3].

Concentrations of toxic metals exceeded the hygienic standards (MPC) established on them for the content of lead, molybdenum, manganese, copper, iron, cobalt, and zinc in water.

Analysis and results: The study of the species composition of algae and their distribution along the Akhangaran River is very relevant today, since the formation and functioning of hydrobiocenoses of the river depend on algal communities. Water quality control in the river is currently one of the acute problems. To solve it, studies were carried out on the distribution of indicator-saprobic species *Bacillariophyta*, *Cyanophyta*, *Chlorophyta* and *Euglenophyta* in the river at monitoring stations (MS) during 2022—2023, and their comparative analysis was carried out.

In our material, among green algae, *Ulothrix zonata* was found along the currents of the Akhangaran River in both normal, filamentous and palmelliform states. The transition of *Ulothrix* to the palmelloid state was preceded by thickening of the cell membrane and slackening, which serves as protection against fouling organisms and increases the stability of cells in the colony. We observed a special case of the formation of abnormal cells at the Tuyabuguz reservoir in blue-green planktonic algae. Cells that multiplied from mid-July to the end of October at a pH of = 7.4 – 7.8 in a mass amount of *Microcystis aeruginosa* underwent significant changes under conditions of dilution with heavy rainfall and a drop in pH to 6.8.

For various ponds and reservoirs in the Tashkent region, the phenomenon of explosive cell destruction was noted in the vegetative species of the genus *Anabaena*. The phenomenon of the formation of “dactylococcoid” cells, similar to that described in *Microcystis aeruginosa* from the Tuyabuguz reservoir, from our observations it can be assumed that the main factor contributing to the formation of abnormal cells in *Microcystis aeruginosa* is the pH of the medium.

Diatoms are most often species rich in the studied flora and are capable of mass species development. In our material, ugly forms have been observed in various species. For example, the genus *Cocconeis*, whose species prefer water that is not polluted, often formed valves with recesses at the poles or with concavity of the valves in the middle. Elements of fine structure remained within normal limits.

Research results show that the number of xeno - and oligosaprobic algae species is decreasing, and the number of beta, alpha, meso-saprobic algae species is increasing from the upper to the middle and lower parts of the river, where polysaprobic algae also appear. All this is due to the supply of highly

contaminated wastewater and an increase in the concentration of organomineral substances.

Calculation of saprobiological indices using formula P. Pantle, N. Bukk (1955) [9] showed that the average annual sum of the frequency of occurrence ($\sum h$) of saprobic algae in the upper part is 167, in the middle part – 298, in the lower part – 363. The average annual frequency of occurrence ($\sum h$) along the river reaches 828.

The sum of the frequency of occurrence (h) and the ratio of the degree of saprobity of algae (s) in the upper part of the Akhangaran River $\sum (h*s)$ is 189.5, in the middle – 484.5 and in the lower – 727.5. The sum of the frequency of occurrence (h) and the ratio of the degree of saprobity of algae (s) of the Akhangaran River $\sum (h*s)$ are 1401.5. The saprobic valence (saprobity index) of S_i in the upper part of the river is 1.13, in the average – 1.62, in the lower – 2.04. The average sum of the saprobity index (S_i) reaches 1.69.

The results of the study showed that along the – river flows, the upper, middle and lower saprobity indices were 1.13; 1.62 and 2.04, respectively. The saprobic zone of the river varied from the alpha-oligosaprobic to the beta', beta-mesosaprobic zone, water quality – from 2nd to 3rd class with discharges 2a – 3a – 3b.

The results of our study on indicator saprobic algae confirm that the Akhangaran River is polluted with organic and mineral substances, which from year to year (2022-2023) worsens the ecological and sanitary condition of the river downstream from top to bottom.

Conclusions. Depending on the occurrence of indicator-saprobic species of algae, we assessed the quality of the water river. The results were as follows: in the upper part of the river the water is clean, in the middle – it is satisfactorily clean, in the lower – it is slightly contaminated.

Thus, the Akhangaran River, used as a source of water supply and recreation, poses a potential health hazard due to the content of toxic elements in the water in quantities significantly exceeding permissible levels.

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